

Digitally-enhanced analogue solution for optical carrier transfer; human intervention-free relocking of the in-loop PLL of the stabilized optical frequency transfer system

The solution described below was developed within the TiFOON 18SIB06 project at AGH University of Science and Technology. This technical note is complementary to the scientific paper:

<https://doi.org/10.24425/mms.2020.134586>

Authors: P. Włodarczyk, P. Krehlik (krehlik@agh.edu.pl), Ł. Śliwczyński.

1. Introduction

The commonly used solution for active cancellation of fiber phase noise in the optical frequency dissemination systems is to arrange a PLL system which control the frequency provided for an acousto-optic modulator compensating the phase noise arising in the fiber. The needed phase error signal is determined basing on a beat note between the local optical frequency reference and signal coming back from the fiber. Because the beat note is generally weak and strongly corrupted by noise, the helper PLL, usually called as a tracking oscillator is added - see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The main part of the phase noise cancellation scheme.

In our perspective of the automated (human intervention free) relocking of the system, it may be pointed out that main PLL relocks automatically thanks to phase-frequency detector used. But the helper PLL (tracking oscillator), which operate with very noisy signal, cannot use such detector and exploits an analogue frequency mixer as the phase comparator. Additionally, the integrator is used in the signal chain to ensure $\pi/2$ DC phase offset, needed for proper operating point of the mixer. Unfortunately, such PLL needs zeroing the integrator during the lock acquisition, usually by the mechanically driven switch parallel to the integrator's capacitor - se Fig. 1.

2. Auto re-locking solution

The human intervention free solution is depicted in Fig. 2. The added charge pump is added for pulling the PLL towards locking condition, by switching for a moment one of the two transistors. The microcontroller is running the algorithm which steer the charge pump, determining the needed action by measuring simultaneously two frequencies: the tracker frequency and the frequency steering the acousto-optic modulator. Analyzing both frequencies the locked and unlocked states may be distinguished, and moreover the desired direction and amount of the integrator pulling may be determined.

The detailed description and evaluation of the solution is published in the paper entitled “A maintenance-free solution for optical frequency transfer”, Metrology and Measurement Systems, vol 27, 2020 <https://doi.org/10.24425/mms.2020.134586>

The algorithm of the supervision and relocking, realized with the STM microcontroller, is depicted in Fig. 3, and its example realization in Fig. 4. The hardware related to the tracking oscillator with the charge pump is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 2. The tracking oscillator with automated relocking.

Fig. 3. Relocking algorithm.

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m_freq_AOM = timer2_ch2*DIV_AOM; // frequency fL measured with timer (in kHz)
if (FR_AOM > 0) freq_beat_desired = abs(2*m_freq_AOM + 10*FR_RS); // in kHz
else freq_beat_desired = abs(-2*m_freq_AOM + 10*FR_RS);
m_freq_TR_prev = m_freq_TR;
m_freq_TR = timer3_ch1*DIV_TR; // frequency fTR measured with timer (in kHz)
tol = (int)abs(FR_TOL*(2*10*FR_AOM+10*FR_RS)/1000); // in kHz
tol_aom = (int)abs(FR_TOL*10*FR_AOM/1000); // in kHz

switch (stan)
{
case TEST:
// something for tests
break;

case ST_COMP:
if (m_freq_TR > freq_beat_desired) stan=ST_DEC;
if (m_freq_TR < freq_beat_desired) stan=ST_INC;
break;

case ST_DEC:
// if trend is correct, nothing is done
if (m_freq_TR > m_freq_TR_prev) // wrong trend
{
if (INVERT ==1) GPIOC->BRR = 1UL<<5; // UP activated
else GPIOC->BRR = 1UL<<4; // DOWN activated
stan=ST_COMP;
}
if (abs(m_freq_TR - freq_beat_desired) < tol) stan=ST_MONITOR;
break;

case ST_INC:
// if trend is correct, nothing is done
if (m_freq_TR < m_freq_TR_prev) //wrong trend
{
if (INVERT ==1) GPIOC->BRR = 1UL<<4; // DOWN activated
else GPIOC->BRR = 1UL<<5; // UP activated
stan=ST_COMP;
}
if (m_freq_TR > freq_beat_desired - tol && m_freq_TR < freq_beat_desired + tol) stan=ST_MONITOR;
// i.e. frequency within tolerance
break;

case ST_MONITOR:
czekaj++;
if (abs(m_freq_TR - freq_beat_desired) < tol) czekaj=0; // i.e. frequency within tolerance
else if (czekaj > WAIT)
{
if (m_freq_TR > freq_beat_desired + tol) stan=ST_COMP;
if (m_freq_TR < freq_beat_desired - tol) stan=ST_COMP;
}
break;
}
}

```

meaning of constants:

DIV_AOM--division factor related to a divider (prescaler) used for reducing f_L frequency before providing to the microcontroller's timer (acting as a frequency meter)

DIV_TR--division factor related to a divider (prescaler) used for reducing f_{TR} frequency before providing to the microcontroller's timer (acting as a frequency meter)

FR_AOM--nominal value of f_L frequency in tens of kHz (with sign)

FR_RS--remote end frequency shift in tens of kHz (with sign)

FR_TOL--relative frequency tolerance in $1E-3$ parts

INVERT--if 1, meaning of UP and DOWN is exchange; should be set 0 or 1 to obtain negative sign of the feedback control loop

WAIT--number of code cycles before entering ST_COMP state

Fig. 4. Example of the algorithm realization.

Fig. 5. Example of the hardware realization.